

ISic0832

The Technitai of Dionysos honour Skymnos

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found before 1890 in the area of the in Neapolis

Coordinates

37.075784, 15.275079

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 7

Physical Description

A fragment of a white marble plaque, intact on the left side, but broken on the other three sides

Dimensions

Height 7-8.5 cm

Width 13.0-13.3 cm

Depth 3.0-3.4 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neat and regular letters of the later Hellenistic period, in some cases with pronounced serifs. Omicron is full-size; omega is closed; epsilon has shorter middle bar; mu has splayed outer hastae; kappa on occasion has short arms; sigma has parallel top and bottom strokes; pi has equal vertical strokes and the horizontal overhangs on both sides.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 9-10 mm

Line 2: 9 mm

Line 3: 9 mm

Line 4: 7-8 mm

Line 5: 8-9 mm

Line 6: incomplete mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [---][τὸ κοινὸν τῶν περιτῶν]
2. Διόνυσον τεχνιτῶν [νστεφανοῖτὸν δεῖνα τοῦ δεῖνα]
3. υἱὸν Σκύμνον, εὐερ[γέτην ἀρετῆς ἔνεκεν καὶ εὐνοίας ἤς]
4. ἔχων διατελεῖ πρὸς [τὸ κοινὸν τῶν περιτῶν Διόνυσον]
5. τεχνιτῶν καὶ κατὰ καλ[οκἀγαθίαν εὐθὺς δέ μετὰ τὰς]

6. σπονδὰς καὶ ζῶντα [καὶ μεταλλάξαντα αὐτὸν ἐπιτῆς]
7. τρίτης [ἀεὶ ἡμέρας τῶν συνόδων ἀναγορεύεσθαι]

Apparatus

Text of Kaibel in IG XIV.12

Sigma of πρὸς read by Kaibel but not visible on stone

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492457

EDCS 39101983

PHI 140303

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